

Supplementary Tables ‘Plasma protein profiles associated with anxiety and/or depressive symptoms in young IBD patients and the effect of cognitive behavioral therapy’

Supplementary Table 1. Proteins associated with mild/severe anxiety and/or depressive symptoms

Protein	Mean difference	Fold Change	Adjusted p-value	Function
LIF-R	0.2959	1.23	0.0014	activation HPA-axis
TNFRSF9	0.7809	1.72	0.0089	development T cells
CST5	0.6408	1.56	0.0158	proteolysis
uPA	0.3723	1.29	0.0288	proteolysis
FGF-23	0.7945	1.73	0.0539	regulator of inflammatory gene expression
MCP-3	0.5492	1.46	0.0742	chemotaxis inflammatory response
TRANCE	0.6485	1.57	0.1159	regulation of T cell immune response
CCL4	0.5138	1.43	0.1203	chemotaxis inflammatory response
TGF-alpha	0.3625	1.29	0.1203	growth factor / epithelial development
MCP-1	0.4163	1.33	0.1393	chemotaxis inflammatory response
GDNF	0.3198	1.25	0.1393	neuron survival and regeneration
HGF	0.3949	1.31	0.1398	growth. motility and morphogenic factor
IL-8	0.5173	1.43	0.1690	pro-inflammatory cytokine. innate response
IL-10RA	0.5918	1.51	0.1833	anti-inflammatory activity
IL-15RA	0.1522	1.11	0.2009	T-cell proliferation
SCF	0.2874	1.22	0.2030	production proinflammatory cytokines/ chemokines
IL-18	0.2991	1.23	0.2030	cell-mediated immunity/IFN- γ production
DNER	0.2775	1.21	0.2030	activator of the NOTCH1 pathway
IL-4	0.3452	1.27	0.2054	activates naïve Tcells/ B. T cell proliferation
TNF-B	0.2527	1.19	0.2211	activated NF-kB pathway
IL-10RB	0.1576	1.12	0.2215	anti-inflammatory activity
4E-BP1	0.2399	1.18	0.2304	protein translation
ADA	0.3732	1.30	0.2431	purine metabolism
CX3CL1	0.3335	1.26	0.2431	chemotaxis/adhesion of T cells to endothelial cells
MCP-4	0.4897	1.40	0.2431	chemotaxis
IL-2RB	0.1014	1.07	0.2799	regulation of growth and differentiation of T&B - Cells.

Note: Fold change reflects mild/severe compared to no anxiety and/or depressive symptoms

Supplementary Table 2. Proteins associated to depressive symptoms in patients < 18 years - unadjusted p value < 0.10

Protein	Beta [CI]	Adjusted R ² *	Unadjusted P-value	Adjusted p-value
VEGFA	-0.069 [-0.118- -0.020]	22.3%	0.0078	0.0523
MCP-4	-0.072 [-0.125- -0.020]	27.4%	0.0092	0.0569
CCL4	-0.067 [-0.117- -0.017]	17.0%	0.0115	0.0638
CXCL6	-0.079 [-0.138- -0.019]	24.1%	0.0121	0.0638
CCL28	-0.049 [-0.087 - -0.012]	32.9%	0.0125	0.0638
IL-10	-0.084 [-0.151- -0.016]	21.9%	0.0176	0.0849
CASP-8	-0.087 [-0.158- -0.016]	16.4%	0.0192	0.0878
MMP-1	-0.095 [-0.177- -0.013]	25.9%	0.0249	0.1084
FGF-5	-0.016 [-0.030- -0.001]	17.4%	0.0379	0.1498
SCF	-0.029 [-0.058- -0.001]	22.9%	0.0418	0.1583
IL-15RA	-0.012 [-0.025-0.001]	17.9%	0.0501	0.1759
CSF-1	-0.016 [-0.033-0.001]	22.9%	0.0555	0.1788
CXCL5	-0.035 [-0.072-0.003]	15.1%	0.0687	0.2124
ARTN	0.032 [-0.004-0.068]	20.3%	0.0773	0.2124
IL-7	-0.031 [-0.066-0.004]	48.0%	0.0783	0.2124

Abbreviations: CI: 95% confidence interval. * adjusted R² reflects the regression model including age and gender as predictors.

Supplementary Table 3. Reliable change index for anxiety and depressive symptoms

	No reliable change	Reliable deterioration (increase in score)	Reliable improvement (decrease in score)
Anxiety symptoms (SCARED or HADS-A)			
CAU	10 (66.7%)	0 (0%)	5 (33.3%)
CBT	5 (38.5%)	0 (0%)	8 (61.5%)
Depressive symptoms (CDI or BDI-II)			
CAU	8 (53.3%)	0 (0%)	7 (46.7%)
CBT	5 (38.5%)	1 (7.7%)	7 (53.8%)

$\chi^2 = 2.227$. $df = 2$. $p = .255$.

$\chi^2 = 1.150$. $df = 2$. $p = .567$.

Note: Numbers in parentheses indicate row percentages. For 2/15 patients allocated to CBT, the Reliable Change Index could not be calculated because 3-month data were incomplete.

**Supplementary Table 4. Proteins levels changed over time within either CBT or CAU group
- unadjusted p value < 0.10**

Group	Protein	Mean difference	Unadjusted p-value	Function
CBT	CCL4	0.287	0.055	chemotaxis inflammatory response
	SLAMF1	0.229	0.056	controlling innate/ adaptive immune responses
	ARTN	0.134	0.070	neurotrophic factor
	DNER	0.108	0.072	activator of the NOTCH1 pathway
	TWEAK	0.177	0.081	induction of inflammatory cytokines
	SCF	0.138	0.085	production proinflammatory cytokines/ chemokines
	CD6	0.647	0.091	t cell activation
	MCP-4	0.267	0.095	chemotaxis
CAU	CXCL11	-0.310	0.071	chemotaxis on interleukin-activated T cells
	SLAMF1	-0.212	0.077	controlling innate/ adaptive immune responses
	IL-18	-0.211	0.084	cell-mediated immunity/IFN- γ production

Supplementary Table 5. Delta proteins levels CBT versus CAU group - unadjusted p value < 0.10

Protein	Mean difference	Fold change	Unadjusted p-value
CCL28	0.33126	-1.25	0.050
CCL25	0.26606	-1.20	0.058
CD40	0.33682	-1.26	0.069
IL-12B	0.31538	-1.24	0.071
CDCP1	0.22496	-1.17	0.075
CD244	0.39847	-1.31	0.078
CXCL6	0.49015	-1.40	0.091